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Research Article

EFFECTIVENESS OF PSYCHOSOCIAL SUPPORT ON CARE BURDEN AMONG CAREGIVERS OF PATIENT WITH MENTAL DISORDER IN SELECTED HOSPITAL DEHRADUN, UTTARAKHAND

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ABSTRACT

Family is a tiny unit that joins to make a society and also is important to individual as it provides benefits to your physical, emotional and mental health that cannot be found anywhere else. The purpose of the study is to provide psychosocial support to reduce the care burden among caregivers of patient with mental disorder. A quantitative research approach was adopted. 50 caregivers were selected under the study through non-probability total enumeration sampling technique from selected hospital of Dehradun, Uttarakhand. Caregiver's basic socio demographic profile was collected through self-structured questionnaire and care burden was assessed through The Zarit Burden Interview Scale. The study finding showed that psychosocial support was effective on the reduction of care burden among caregivers of patient with mental disorder.

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INTRODUCTION

Family, a gathering of people joined by the ties of marriage, blood, or appropriation, comprising a solitary family and cooperating with one another in their separate social positions, normally those of companions, guardians, youngsters, and kin¹. The family performs distinctive significant capacities with regards to its people².

If all the members are healthy in family, so their physical and mental health will be in good state, according to the Maslow hierarchy every individual needs- shelter, love, security, emotional stability and free from stress.

The wellbeing of family members depends upon the happiness of individual member of family and also if anyone among the family is sick it affects the whole family³. As stated by WHO that *health* is a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity¹. Based on this we can draw a conclusion that mental illness among member of family does not affect only that particular family but also it has its impact on the whole society.

Health especially, mental health is a state of well-being in which an individual realizes his or her own abilities, can cope

with the normal stresses of life, can work productively and is able to make a contribution to his or her community. Around 450 million individuals overall are experiencing some mental or social issue as per the WHO. As per the evidence accessible, in India, around 190–200/1000 population have a psychiatric or mental disorder, this records for about 20% of the whole population⁴.

Family often bears substantial amount of care burden of any psychiatric illness and the burden of mental illness continues to rise, posing serious health risks as well as severe social, human rights, and economical consequences. The family assumes an extremely crucial part under the watchful eye of a mentally sick patient⁵.

Medine Koc, et.al, (2020) had done a study to determining care burden and psychiatric symptom level in caregiver of schizophrenia patient. It is suggested that the family individuals are directed to design exercises that will permit the family individuals to unwind and cover their own necessities⁶.

As caregivers of mentally ill are prone to have care burden as mentioned earlier if we are able to manage their psychological stress it will be beneficial to achieve good mental health among caregivers as well as it provides better outcome in treatment of

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the patient. Based on this researcher felt a need of providing psychosocial support to reduce their care burden.

Carol J Whit latch, et.al, (2018) had done a study on educational program and psychosocial support needs of caregivers with dementia patient. The sample size were 60 and were assessed by Zarit burden interview scale. The study result shows the educational program can help to ensure the person and family centered care was maintained and psychosocial support need was effective for understanding the caregiver's burden.⁷

Current study provided psychosocial support to reduce the care burden among caregivers of patient with mental disorder.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Research Approach

A quantitative research approach was adopted for this study.

Research Design

Quasi-Experimental Design (Time series design)

Setting

The current research was done in Psychiatry unit of the Himalayan Hospital of Dehradun.

Population

In the present study, the population consists of all the caregivers of patient with mental disorder admitted in psychiatric ward in Himalayan Hospital Dehradun, Uttarakhand

Samples

The sample of present study consist of all caregivers of patients with mental disorder admitted in psychiatric ward in Himalayan hospital Jolly grant, Dehradun, Uttarakhand who comply with the requirements.

Sampling Technique

In the present study, all the samples who fulfill the inclusion criteria are recruited using the non- probability total enumeration sampling technique.

Sample Size

The calculated sample size was 43 at 97% confidence interval considering 5% assumed error, enrolled 50caregivers in the study.

Development and description of Tool

Section A: Socio-demographical profile of caregivers

Section B: The Zarit Burden Interview Scale

This tool was developed in English and Hindi. This was standardized scale to check the care burden of the caregivers. The ZBI 22 was created in 1980 by Zarit, Reever, and Bacg Peterson⁸. There are five response possibilities for each topic, ranging from "never" to "nearly always". The ZBI was categorized under four aspects such as little or no burden, Mild to moderate burden, Moderate to severe burden and severe burden.

Ethical Consideration

Ethical permission was acquired from the Ethical Committee of Swami Rama Himalaya University to conduct the present study. Administrative permission was obtained from the Principal, Himalayan College of Nursing and Head of Department (HOD) of Psychiatry department, Himalayan Hospital, SRHU to conduct the study in Psychiatric ward. Informed written consent was taken from all the caregivers of patient with mental disorder before collection of data. Affirmation was lay down to the subjects that the secrecy of every person would be maintained.

RESULT

The majority of the study participants (46%) were between the ages of 31-46 years. More than half participants (54%) were male. More than half participants (78%) were married. More than half of participants (38%) had secondary education. Most of the participants (36%) having business. More than half of participants 39(78%) had monthly income between 15001 and above. More than half of participants 44(88%) were >5years of duration of caregiver. Most of the participants 20(40%) were parents/Sibling. Majority of caregivers 29(58%) belong to joint family. Most of participants 37(74%) belongs to Hindu religion. Most of the participants 32(64%) were lived in urban area

Figure No 1 Effectiveness of Psychosocial Support on Care Burden among caregivers of patient with mental disorder

(N= 50)

After administration of Psychosocial Support, there was reduction in the care burden that is on day fourth, most of the caregivers 43(86%) were come under mild to moderate burden, four (8%) were come under moderate to severe burden, three (6%) were come under little or no burden.

There was progressive reduction of mean scores from pre-test to last post-test as pre-test score is 62.68± 9.217 followed by post-test score of day fourth 31.44±6.655, post test score of day eleventh 24.78±6.319 and post test score of day eighteen 21.68±5.016.

DISCUSSION

The current study finding showed that the F value was 338.920 and p value was 0.044 (3) at 0.05 significant level which proves that the psychosocial support on care burden among caregivers of patient with mental disorder was effective.

These findings were congruent to the study conducted by Dadson DA, et.al, (2018) also reported that counselling services and psych education to help caregiver to manage their negative experiences and reduced the care burden⁹. Chien W.T, (2013)revealed that there was a marked improvement in caregivers and it help to manage their daily activity and also concluded that psycho education for caregivers will effective in reduction in care burden and hospitalization of patients¹⁰.

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